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APPLICATION #	RECEIPT DATE / TIME	ATTORNEY DOCKET #
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Title of Invention

The use and importance of GenAi in the construction of the highly advanced 5th Generation Fighter Aircrafts

Application Information

APPLICATION TYPE	International Application (PCT) for filing in the US receiving office	PATENT #	-
CONFIRMATION #	3007	FILED BY	AURNAB DUTTA ROY
PATENT CENTER #	70580352	FILING DATE	-
CUSTOMER #	-	APPLICANT NAME	AURNAB DUTTA ROY
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Documents

TOTAL DOCUMENTS: 1

DOCUMENT	PAGES	DESCRIPTION	SIZE (KB)
PatentFile26052025.pdf	4	Abstract	110 KB

Digest

DOCUMENT	MESSAGE DIGEST(SHA-512)
PatentFile26052025.pdf	315A7FDFDF10ED8DDDE06A0299F391A4BD4B6BD74D93C302 C1E5FD0975A86A3EB59AA7C2EA319022D11FFAE76881FC41 62A34B77796AB042D53A4D9B6730F244

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